

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11251001

TRACING ENVIRONMENTAL PATTERNS AND HUMAN ACTIVITIES VIA THE CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS OF SOIL STRATIGRAPHY: THE MYCENAEAN SPERCHEIOS-VALLEY ARCHAEOLOGICAL PROJECT (LAMIA, GREECE)

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Received: 01/05/2024

Accepted: 18/06/2024

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ABSTRACT

The research goal of this paper is to present geological data in context to the archaeological interpretation of land use of the Lamia Acropolis based on soil samples extracted from two test trenches on the site. By applying particle size analysis, p-XRF analysis and SEM examination an interpretation of the chemical foot-print maintained in the soil samples were studied. Particle size analysis provided data concerning composition by separating different ranges of sizes and determining their relative proportion by weight. In addition, p-XRF and SEM analysis were used to examine chemical composition. The results are presented in an attempt to classify the archaeologically related soil samples by means of use, type of formation, or chronological period. Overall, soil analysis from the excavation area was realized for 51 soil samples extracted from the 13 layers of the stratigraphy.

KEYWORDS: environment, geology, XRF, stratigraphy, soil characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The five-year Mycenaean Spercheios-Valley Archaeological Project (MY.SPE.AR.), realized in the Lamia Municipality in central Greece, started in 2018 including extensive and intensive archaeological survey, aerial reconnaissance, geophysical survey, and targeted excavation and digital technology in order to locate, identify, and map all Mycenaean sites in the region of the Spercheios valley. The research area, the Spercheios valley, stretches for some 80 km east-west, wedged in-between Thessaly and Boeotia, dividing the regions of central and southern Greece, and allowing only for a narrow shoreline passageway between them. It covers a flat plane of 370 sq. km, is nearly land-locked, surrounded on three sides and protected by mountain ranges that delineate clear regional boundaries, allowing, however, eastward access to the sea. The My.SPE.AR. project is implemented under the dual directorship of the Ephorate of Antiquities of Fthiotida and Evritania with Dickinson College, assisted by the scientific coalition of the Geophysics Laboratory of the Aristotle University of

Thessaloniki, the Architectural Design and Research Laboratory of the Democritus University of Thrace, the Laboratory of Archaeometry of the University of the Peloponnese and the support of the Municipality of Lamia and the Mycenaean Foundation.

Key parameters in the implementation of the MYSPEAR program are: recording of positions using a GNSS geodetic system (Topcon GR5), collection and digitization of aerial photographs from the Army Geographical Service (G.Y.S.) as well as special-ized maps (archaeological, geographical/topographical, geological, geoseismological, hydrological etc.). During the first two years, with the participation of the Laboratory of Archaeometry of the University of Peloponnese, 27 sites were mapped based on publications from the Archaeological Journal of the Ephorate of Antiquities. The preliminary archaeological surface survey at these sites as well as a geophysical survey in the area of the hill of the castle of Lamia, Akrolamia, were carried out in the summer of 2018 and 2019 (Fig. 1) (Malaperdas *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1. Satellite image - Lamia Castle (Sentinel 2)

During the excavation period of 2019, two test trenches were created on the Lamia Acropolis where the Lamia castle is located. The castle of Lamia, or Akrolamia, is located on top of a hill in the center of the city, at the highest point, at 210m from sea level. The rocky hill was a strategic position for monitoring and controlling the valley of Spercheios with a view of the valley and the peaks of the mountains Kallidromos, Parnassos and Gionas (Maggidis C. *et al*, 2022). The Acropolis extends over the hilltop across of 16 acres

with a N-S slope. The slopes of the hill are steep and in places very steep ($>45^\circ$) (Sillaios, Bilas, & Karapetsas, 2007). The castle of Lamia consists of a polygonal enclosure that is internally divided into three parts. From the preserved parts of the enclosure of Akrolamia, the castle dates back to the 6th century BC. It was influenced by different conquerors, Byzantines, Franks, Catalans and Ottoman Turks. It was declared a historical monument in 1922 by Royal decree

and was used as a recruit center until 1941 (Papakonstantinou, 1994). During the excavation of Professor Hourmouziadis (Hourmouziadis, 1979) in the area outside the modern fortification walls, findings indicated that the area may have been used as a fortress even from the Mycenaean era.

The systematic inhabitation of an area by humans significantly influences the environment of an area in terms of the landscape, including disturbance in vegetation, animal population, cultivation impacts, existence of fire etc. (Butzer, 1982). Centuries of continuous human occupation in an area also leaves its impact in the soil composition leaving chemical markers (Oonk et al, 2009). This accumulation of anthropogenic matter makes the soils differ from natural soils while the chemical markers offer insight on land usage in the area. In this aspect and considering how organic matter accumulates excessively in areas such as farmhouses or workhouses, higher values of iron in soil samples can be expected (Biswas, 2020). Reduction which occurs during oxidation of organic material favors dissolution of iron minerals that in the presence of oxygen precipitates from ferrous to ferric substances (Karkanis, 2018).

Studies realized in housing and farm areas showed an enrichment of both calcium and strontium, most likely explained by the lime in house structures for covered and closed housing areas (Middleton and Price, 1996) (Gauss et al, 2013). Higher levels of calcium in the soil is a significant indicator in archaeological soils suggesting areas of food preparation, middens or even dump areas, sites mainly for bone and ash disposal (Carr 1982). Calcium can also signify shell content, either shell sand used in farming or from teeth and bones in dump areas and cooking areas (Vranová et al., 2015).

In situ burning areas show higher concentrations of P, K, Ca and Fe (Middleton, 2014). A closer look at potassium enhancements in soil sediments is associated with archaeological deposits with higher concentration of organic matter, ash and charcoal (Wilson et al, 2006). Potassium is an essential indicator for building construction (Hejcman et al., 2011; Hejcman et al., 2013a) as well as cooking ash and decaying animal remains (Wilson et al, 2006). Taking under consideration that K and Ca are highly concentrated in manure, soil enriched in K and Ca, has been shown to be related to manuring (Oonk et al, 2009). On that note calcium and strontium have been shown present especially in hearths and houses, with the highest concentrations of calcium found in hearth areas, in opposition to arable fields and gardens where calcium did

not show any remarkable enhancements (Wilson et al, 2008). Strontium can therefore be connected to anthropogenic deposits providing information for presence of animal manure, bones fragments and house waste (Biswas and Ramgopal, 2020). The goal of this paper is to develop an approach to understanding and interpreting compositional trends from the stratigraphy of archaeological soils.

2. METHODS

This can be realized by examining the chemical composition and granular analysis of soils extracted from the archaeological section. The results provide for presenting the geological data in context to the archaeological interpretation of land use. The initial attempt in situ, using a portable XRF, did not have the anticipated results therefore sampling is considered the optimal method for further analysis in the laboratory. The approach has been applied on an excavation wall within the Asklepieion of Ancient Thouria, located in the southern Peloponnese, that had a very interesting stratigraphy of over 7 layers on a wall of over 3 meters and macroscopically featured great diversity from a geological and archaeological scope (Panagiotidis et al., 2020).

During the excavation period of 2019 the the extensive survey continued in the wider region and two test trenches were opened. In the center of the city of Lamia, the capital of the Fthiotida prefecture, rises the Akrolamia hill, the Acropolis of the city where the Archaeological Museum of Fthiotida is located today. The Archaeological Museum is situated within the 19th century building built during the reign of King Otto of Greece. Two test trenches were excavated in the Castle court, trench A west of the Museum building and trench B east of it (Fig. 2).

Soil samples were extracted for this study from Trench A with dimensions 2.40m x 3.40m. Site selection for Trench A was chosen following the results of the geophysical survey from the previous year. Trench A, located west of the main building of the castle/fortress produced during this preliminary excavation, in the upper layers mostly tile fragments were unearthed, as well as pottery sherds, body fragments, bases and handles dated in post-Byzantine period, some of them decorated with glaze. The tile fragments were mostly non characteristic and on the upper layers of the trench signalling maybe a debris pit. The excavation spanned over a three-week period.

Figure 2. "Akrolamia" Lamia Castle Trench A where stratigraphy study was applied is the orthogonal red T [Google Earth]

2.1. Sampling

The soil samples were collected during the excavation in real time as the digging proceeded. They were extracted using a steel trowel collected into plastic bags, sealed, tagged and stored. Macroscopically the section stratigraphy was separated according to the observed diversification at the time of the ongoing excavation, e.g., soil density, description, color, findings, features etc. In total 9 layers were distinguished (not counting the top surface layer), a few of which overlapped or were within the previous (Figure 3). For example, in the western side of Layer 7, consecutive layers of plaster and stone walls are found, suggesting the collapse of a one-story building; the surface of the layer on that side continues deeper below the stone tumble. Layers 8 and 9 are particularly disturbed, thus leading to the collection of additional

samples from multiple different loci, in order to better characterize the properties of each layer (Layer 8: Unit 1: floors, Unit 2: pit, Unit 3: small pit; Layer 9: Unit 1: big hole, Unit 2: layer below floor, Unit 3:). Figure 3 is a drawing under scale of the site and sampling stratigraphy created in situ to assist the samples documentation.

The samples were extracted from the soil surrounding certain features such as possible hearths or pits unweathered. From each layer samples were removed following the excavator's guidance depending on the findings or "activity" in that layer. A total of 85 samples were collected from the 9 differentiated layers, 47 of which were selected for further analysis. It should be highlighted that no samples were collected from Layer 2, since the layer was macroscopically characterized to consist of broken tiles.

Figure 3. Stratigraphy drawing Trench A

All samples were examined macroscopically to determine their visual properties. Layer 3 was proven to be a thin layer of solid plaster; therefore, no further analysis was carried out on the samples of this layer. From each of the samples of the remaining seven layers approximately 200gr were used for grain size distribution analysis. The analysis was realized using a system of 6 sieves with a variation in mesh sized from 1,94mm to 0,062mm. The soils were vigorously shaken, and the retained amounts documented for the 47 representative samples and 6 sieves including the base powder.

The XRF analysis of the soil samples was carried out using approximately 20gr of soil separated from each sample bag and slightly grinded using a marble mortar and pestle. The grinded sample was then pressed into pellets and dried at 70°C for 8 hours. The elemental concentration of the samples was determined by means of energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) measurements using the Epsilon 5 benchtop spectrometer by Panalytical of the XRF Laboratory, Institute of Nuclear and Particle Physics of the National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos" (Manousakas et al, 2018). This spectrometer is equipped with a 600W Sc/W-target X-ray tube (100 kV and 24 mA maximum high voltage and current, respectively), whereas a Germanium crystal is used for X-ray detection with resolution 140 eV at 5.9 keV. Between the X-ray tube and the specimen, a set of secondary targets is inserted (pure element metallic or

pure pressed compound materials) in reflection Cartesian and polarization geometry, which provides the reduction of spectral background and, mainly, the monochromatization of the exciting radiation (Schramm, 2016).

All measurements were performed under vacuum conditions. The operating conditions are presented in Table 1. Several certified reference materials (CRMs) were served to generate calibration curves of normalized characteristic X-ray intensities versus the concentration of analyte. In particular, the following 11 multi-elemental standards were employed: ISE886, IAEA10-ISE918, IAEA 09-ISE951, ISE952, IAEA04-ISE954, IAEA CU-2006-06, SARM42, GBW07307, BAM-S005A, NIST679, NIST620.

Finally, in order to better evaluate some of the light elements that are of particular interest and could not be determined by XRF (primarily Mg and P), SEM/EDS analysis was carried out on selected samples from each layer. A Scanning Electron Microscope by JEOL (JSM-6510LV) coupled with an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer for quantitative analysis (Oxford Systems) was used. The analytical data were obtained by INCA software. The measurements were performed on fresh cuts of the prepared pellets with a flat surface, at 20 kV accelerating voltage, for 120 s count time. More detailed information on the analytical accuracy of the set up are described in length at Moropoulou et al. (2018).

Table 1. Operating conditions of Epsilon 5 for ceramic samples analysis

Secondary target	High voltage (kV)	Current (mA)	Detected compounds / elements	Measuring time (s)
CaF ₂	35	17.1	SiO ₂ , K ₂ O	300
Ge	65	9.2	CaO, TiO ₂ , V, Cr, MnO, Fe ₂ O ₃ , Ni, Cu, Zn	300
Mo	100	6	As, Se, Br, Rb, Sr, Y, Zr, Pb, Th	300
Al ₂ O ₃	100	6	Ba, La, Ce, Nd	600

3. RESULTS

Each of the selected samples was examined macroscopically and characterized based on structure, color and content (Table 2). Sediment color, recorded using

the standardized Munsell system, provided information on source (primary coloration) and may reflect diagenetic causes such as biochemical alterations (Shackley, 1981). As mentioned before, Layer 3 was shown to be a homogeneous plaster layer.

Table 2. Macroscopic characterization of section stratigraphy

Layer/Sample #	Soil Density	Description	Color
L1/1	Granular, dry friable	Small white stones, roots, leaves (dry), small charcoal fragments. Few stones and ceramic fragments.	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L1/2	Granular friable low consistency	Few roots, few small ceramic fragments, small white stones, small black stones,	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L1/3	Granular	A number of stones, few small ceramic fragments, small white stones and a number of very small charcoal fragments, shell fragments.	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L1/4	Granular, dry friable	Large stones (4cm, 2.5cm & 1.5cm), white rock details (plaster) few (2-3) pieces of charcoal (5mm) few ceramic fragments, one shell fragment	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L1/5	Granular, friable	Very few ceramic fragments, clay, pieces of plaster and 3 charcoal fragments (1cm, 1cm 0.5cm)	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L3/1	Solid, hard	Plaster layer. White and grey with small grey stones	
L3/2	Solid	Plaster layer. White and grey with small grey stones	
L4/1	Dry coarse	Few ceramic fragments, white plaster fragments, roots, stones large and small.	2.5Y 5/2 Grayish brown
L4/2	Coarse, granular	Many pebbles, small bone fragments	2.5Y 4/2 Dark Grayish Brown
L4/3	Coarse	ceramic fragments, small stones.	2.5Y 5/3 Light olive brown
L4/4	Dry coarse	Bones, ceramic fragments, plaster fragments, one metal nail.	2.5Y 5.3 Light olive brown
L4/5	Dry coarse	Charcoal fragments, stones, ceramic fragments, roots, large bone fragments, glazed pottery fragments.	2.5Y 5/2 Grayish brown
L5/1	Dry coarse	Large stones, bone fragments, charcoal fragments. White stones, grey and black stones. Few small thin roots and ceramic fragments.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L5/2	Dry coarse	Ceramic fragments, bone fragments, stone black.	2.5Y 5.3 Light olive brown
L5/3	Dry coarse	Thin roots, many charcoal fragments, ceramic fragments, pebbles, stones, white plaster fragments, tooth (1cm), bone fragments.	2.5Y 5/2 Grayish brown
L5/4	Dry, coarse, friable	One large bone fragment 4cm. Fine roots and additional bone fragments. Visible burnt layer. Charcoal fragments, ceramic fragments	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L5/5	Coarse and dry	Charcoal fragments large and small (1cm). Stones: black, grey, orange and yellow. Roots, bone thin and small. ceramic fragments (3cm). Plaster and tile fragments.	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray

L5/6	Coarse	Shells 1,3 cm and 0,5cm. Large stones, charcoal fragments, plaster fragments.	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L5/7	Granular	Burnt, black, many long roots. Ceramic fragments, many small stones, large number of charcoal fragments (red brown burnt)	2.5Y 4/1 Dark gray
L6/1	Medium, moist	Large number of ceramic fragments (one glazed 1.5cm). Larger and small charcoal fragments. Many stones from 3cm and less, roots thin and long. Small bone shreds.	2.5Y 5/2 Grayish brown
L7/1	Dry coarse	Tile pieces, ceramic sherd, stones, bone charcoal fragment.	2.5Y 5/2 Grayish brown
L7/2	Dry coarse, friable	Visible charcoal fragments and dust. Significant number of stones.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L7/3	Dry coarse	Shells, large tile, plaster and roots.	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L8/U1/1	Granular, very dry	Many stones appr. 1cm	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L8/U1/2	Granular, dry	Very large stones 10cm and less. Very few white spots. Yellow white stones. One small black painted ceramic fragment (0.8cm)	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L8/U1/3	Granular, dry	Large stones and hard conglomerates of yellow gray material	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L8/U1/4	Granular	Small ceramic fragments 1.5cm, smaller friable ceramic clay fragments. Black small stones and plaster. Small charcoal fragments >4mm. White stones. Yellow clay conglomerates	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L8/U1/5	Granular	Yellowish texture, many small stones, white spots, yellow conglomerates, roots.	2.5Y 7/2 Light gray
L8/U1/6	Granular	Small ceramic fragments 1.5cm, smaller friable ceramic fragments. Black small stones and plaster	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L8/U2/1U1/	Coarse	Large stones, white spots, small charcoal fragments, white friable stones.	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L8/U2/2	Coarse	Large stones, white spots, small charcoal fragments, white friable stones and ceramic fragments.	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L8/U2/3	Coarse	Large stones grey ceramic (small) fragments, tile fragments 5cm and shells.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L8/U3/1	Dry coarse	Yellowish fragments, charcoal, bones, white (plaster) stones.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L9/U1/1	Granular, dry friable	Plaster, large pieces of charcoal. Bone fragment, many roots.	2.5Y 5/3 Light olive brown
L9/U1/2	Granular, dry friable	Small bones, lots of charcoal, fragile yellowish fragments	10YR 5/3 Brown
L9/U1/3	Granular, dry friable	Bones and one large fragment (15cm). Small and larger stones, roots, charcoal.	2.5Y 5/4 Light olive brown
L9/U2/1	Coarse	Large stones, small charcoal fragments, small shell fragments.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L9/U2/2	Coarse	Tile fragments, stones large and small. Some small charcoal fragments and plaster spots.	2.5Y 7/3 Pale yellow
L9/U2/3	Coarse	ceramic fragments, one small bone fragment, many grey stones small and large.	2.5Y 7/2 Light gray
L9/U2/4	Coarse	Stones, large and small. Bone fragments, shells, roots, plaster and yellowish stones.	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L9/U3/1	Granular	Significant number of stones. Many large stones (4cm, 2cm, 3cm etc). Plaster and ceramic fragments. Bone fragment and shells.	2.5Y 5/3 Light olive brown
L9/U3/2	Granular, friable	Many stones, large plaster fragments, shell fragments, one small charcoal fragment. Small ceramic fragment	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown
L9/U3/3	Dry, granular, friable	Small ceramic fragments, yellow white stones and large stones	2.5Y 6/3 Light yellowish brown

L9/U3/4	Granular, friable	Many stones, large number of plaster conglomerates, small charcoal fragment	2.5Y 6/2 Light brownish gray
L9/U3/5	Granular, friable	Many stones, a number of plaster conglomerates as well as ceramic fragments and charcoal fragments	2.5Y 5/3 Light olive brown
L9/U3/6	Granular, friable	Many stones, many plaster fragments of various sizes, long dry thin roots. Small white fragments.	2.5Y 5/3 Light olive brown

Figure 4. Representative images of sample L5/7 under FOM microscope, x50 magnification (left: ceramic fragment; right: charcoal fragments).

Based on the grain size distribution analysis, an overall similar distribution among the layers and consistency from fine sand to coarse sand is noted (Table 3, Fig. 5). In most layers' consistency is over 50% coarse sand. It is interesting to note that the two lower layers (Layer 8 and 9), despite their greater depth,

show a significantly higher amount of coarse sand compared to the other layers. This pattern corroborates the macroscopic observations, which showed a large number of stone, mortar, ceramic and bone fragments on these layers, and can be attributed to a stronger human presence.

Table 3. Mean values of grain pass% per layer

Layer # Sieve Size(mm)	L1	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9
1.94	57.9	56.6	58.7	48.1	51.2	61.8	62.1
0.93	35.5	31.1	33.7	27.1	30.3	39.0	37.6
0.466	22.2	17.3	19.6	15.1	18.0	21.7	19.3
0.263	13.6	9.5	10.5	6.6	10.0	10.8	9.5
0.122	7.3	4.4	4.2	2.4	2.4	4.0	3.8
0.062	3.1	1.5	1.1	0.3	0.1	0.9	1.1

Figure 5. Grain Particle Analysis Diagram

The chemical composition for each sample is presented in Table 1 in the Appendix. The compositional trends for Fe, Ca, K, Rb and Sr were examined using scatter plots based on the XRF data. From the chemical compositions measured it is noticeable in the scatter plot that although the iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) vs silica oxide (SiO_2) concentration for the majority of the samples remain within the range from 18 to 38 wt% for the silica oxides and 2.4 to 4 wt% for the iron oxides, a positive correlation for the iron content versus the silica content is distinguishable in all layers, apart from layer 7 (Fig. 6). These higher values of iron oxide can be related to the anthropogenic activities that accumulate organic matter such as farmhouses, human

workhouses etc. (Biswas, 2020). Taking under consideration the continuous use of land of the Akrolamia hill and the findings during the excavation, the chemical behavior as far as iron content is concerned correlates to the findings and signifies the enrichment of the soil content due to former human activities (Karkanas, 2018). Additionally, in the case of Fe and Si content as Si increases (finer sediments) so does the iron which makes us believe that the finer sediments are enriched in iron where Si is more the 40%; an exception to the above stands for L5, L6 where Fe remains the same while the sediment becomes finer.

Figure 6. Bi-plot of the ratio of SiO₂ concentration versus Fe₂O₃ for the identified stratigraphic layers

When examining calcium oxide (CaO) vs silica oxide (SiO₂) concentration, the higher overall content in calcium in all samples is observed in Unit 1 of Layer 8 (L8/U1) (Fig. 7). The other layers present a low variation for calcium oxide among them while overall the variation in calcium content through the 7 layers extends from 13.4 wt% (L1) to 38.6 wt% (L4). Higher concentrations of calcium are present in dump areas as well as middens or cooking areas (Carr, 1982). Specifically, in the case of L8/U1, this conclusion coincides with the macroscopical observation during the excavation where the mentioned layer along with layers L8/U2 and L9/U2, have a more yellowish hue (2.5Y 7/3 Pale Yellow) related to the other layers (Table 2).

Layer 9/U2 also has a larger variation among sample measurements as far as calcium is concerned. This

broader variation along with the elevated calcium oxide values among the analyzed samples, ranging from 21.1 wt% to 34.6 wt% also corresponds to the excavation log where L9/U2 is referred to as the layer beneath L8/U1 and is considered the layer between the final stones before the bedrock. The lack of bones and shells which were more dominant in the higher layers as well as the small number of pottery fragments and a significant occurrence of plaster could further suggest a destruction layer which would coincide with the variation in calcium content. It should be noted though that the variation is very close to that of other layers but is the largest. The higher calcium content is consistent to the soil's yellow color as with layers L8/U1 and L8/U2 (Table 2).

Figure 7. Bi-plot of the ratio of SiO₂ concentration versus CaO for the identified stratigraphic layers

Potassium (P) is examined for our samples in two plots vs calcium (Ca) and iron (Fe) (Figs. 8 & 9). It is noticeable that the results seem to create two groups that behave similarly for calcium and iron. In both cases the higher content in potassium is correlated to the same layer samples with higher content in iron.

These potassium enhancements can be associated with archaeological deposits with higher concentration of organic matter, such as ash and charcoal which confirms the macro geomorphological observations (Selvaraj et al., 2024).

Figure 8. Bi-plot of the concentration K₂O versus CaO for the identified stratigraphic layers

Figure 9. Bi-plot of the Fe₂O₃ concentration versus K₂O for the identified stratigraphic layers

Elevated levels of strontium and rubidium can indicate an area where fire was used. This coincides with the observations of the excavator where samples from layers L8/U1 and L9/U1 as well as L7 where evidence of pits perhaps firing pits can be verified from

the elevated levels of the two elements. It should be noted that elevated levels of these elements point to anthropogenic deposits which are expected in such an urban environment.

Figure 10. Bi-plot of the Sr concentration versus Rb for the identified stratigraphic layers

Fig. 11 shows the variation of the concentration of selected elements (based on SEM/EDS or XRF values for the light and heavy elements, respectively) through the various layers of the trench under study. The concentration of both phosphorus and potassium shows a significant increase at a depth between 1.5 and 2.0 m from the top surface, suggesting that Layer 6 - and to a lesser degree Layer 7 - is the most enriched in organic matter. It should be noted that Layer 6 also presents the highest concentration of sulphur (Table 3

of the Appendix), which can be related to the high presence of organic matter, as well.

The concentration of zinc presents the exact same pattern; zinc enrichment due to manuring is well documented (Alloway, 2013; Genova et al., 2022), therefore it can be assumed that during these periods there was a significant increase in the agricultural use of the area. Copper, which is also strongly associated with the past agricultural land-use, is also significantly enriched in the same layers, although its peak is at a slightly lower depth.

Figure 11. Concentration of P_2O_5 , K_2O , Cu and Zn through the identified layers of the trench

4. CONCLUSION & FUTURE AIMS

In the development of this methodological approach to tracing environmental patterns and human activities via the chemical synthesis of soil stratigraphy and this study in trench A the fluctuations, even if small, in the chemical signature of the layers come to agree with the granular analysis as well as the macroscopic fluctuations observed during the excavation itself.

Essentially in the case of trench A, where no significant variations in grain distribution or archaeological findings were established, through this methodological approach we evaluated sequences of historical and modern debris in order to reveal land use or activity in the area.

The combination of standard field archaeology approaches, mainly macroscopical observation and drawings, when assisted with grain size and chemical characterization highlight patterns associated with environmental or anthropogenic events.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, V.V. Panagiotidis and N. Zacharias; methodology, V.V. Panagiotidis, E. Palamara; Formal analysis, V.V. Panagiotidis, E. Palamara, K. Tsampa, S. Papagiannis; writing – original draft preparation, V.V. Panagiotidis.; writing – review and editing, E. Palamara, N. Zacharias, C. Maggidis; supervision, N. Zacharias, E. Karantzali, C. Maggidis; funding acquisition, N. Zacharias All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.” Please turn to the CRediT taxonomy for the term explanation. Authorship must be limited to those who have contributed substantially to the work reported.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was implemented within the scope of the “Exceptional Laboratory Practices in Cultural Heritage: Upgrading Infrastructure and Extending Research Perspectives of the Laboratory of Archaeometry”, a co-financed by Greece and the European Union project under the auspices of the program “Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation” NSRF 2014-2020.

REFERENCES

- Alloway, B. (eds) *Heavy Metals in Soils* (2013) *Environmental Pollution*, vol 22. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4470-7_2
- Biswas, Ramgopal. (2020). Estimation of intensity of settlement activities in the Early Medieval Hillfort Královice according to accumulation of anthropogenic elements in the soil, 10.13140/RG.2.2.27371.57121.
- Carr C., *Handbook on soil resistivity surveying: Interpretation of data from earthen archeological sites*, 1982. Evanston, Ill.: Center for American Archeology 2 Press.
- Genova, G., Della Chiesa, S., Mimmo, T., Borruso, L., Cesco, S., Tasser, E., Matteazzi, A. and Niedrist, G. (2022) Copper and zinc as a window to past agricultural land-use. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 424 (2022) 126631.
- Karantzali, E. 2016. "A Middle Helladic apsidal house at Frantzi in the Spercheios valley. Stratigraphic evidence of the MH III-LH I period." In: *Mittei-lungen des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts Athenische Abteilung* 129/130 (2014/2015): 37-75.
- Karantzali, E. 2013. "Mycenaeans within the Spercheios Valley: the Inhabitations at Frantzis and Lygaria." In: *Φιλική Συνεδρία - Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology for Mario Benzi*, edited by Graziado, G., R. Gyglielmino, V. Lenuzza & S. Vitale, BAR International Series 2460, Oxford: Archaeopress, 139-53.
- Karkanias, P., and P. Goldberg. 2018. *Reconstructing Archaeological Sites: Understanding the Geoarchaeological Matrix*. Oxford: Wiley Blackwell.
- Liritzis, I., and Zacharias, N. 2010. *Portable XRF for Use in Archaeology*, in *XRF Technology and Modern Applications*, Εκδόσεις Springer-Verlag, S. Shackley (ed.).
- Maggidis, C., E. Karantzali, and A. Psyhas (2022). "Reassessing a Peripheral Geopolitical Vacuum: The Case for a Mycenaean Palace State in the Spercheios Valley Region." In K. Żebrowska, A. Ulanowska, K. Lewartowski (eds.), *7th Conference in Aegean Archaeology* (University of Warsaw, Poland, June 6-7, 2019), *Symposium Egejskie, Papers in Aegean Archaeology* 4, University of Warsaw Press, 141-151.
- Malaperdas, G., C. Maggidis, E. Karantzali, N. Zacharias (2022). "The Habitation Model Trend Calculation (MTC): Ancient Topography - The Mycenaean Spercheios Valley Case Study." *Interdisciplinaria Archaeologica* 13(1), 29-39. DOI: 10.24916/iansa.2022.1.3
- Manousakas M., Diapouli E., Papaefthymiou H., Kantarelou V., Zarkadas C., Kalogridis A.-C., Karydas A.-G., Eleftheriadis K., XRF characterization and source apportionment of PM10 samples collected in a coastal city, *X-Ray Spectrometry*, 47 (2018) 190-200.
- Moropoulou, A., Zacharias, N., Delegkou, E.T., Apostolopoulou, M., Palamara, E., Kolaiti, A. (2018) OSL mortar dating to elucidate the construction history of the Tomb Chamber of the Holy Aedicule of the Holy Sepulchre in Jerusalem, *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, 19: 80-91.
- Oonk, S., Slomp, C. P. and Huisman, D.J. (2009), *Geochemistry as an aid in archaeological prospection and site interpretation: current issues and research directions*. *Archaeol. Prospect.*, 16: 35-51. <https://doi.org/10.1002/arp.344>
- Panagiotidis V. V., Malaperdas G., Valantou V. & Zacharias N. 2020. Environmental aspects of ancient city planning: a pilot study on Ancient Thouria in the Peloponnese, Greece, *STAR: Science & Technology of Archaeological Research*
- Papakonstantinou, M. F. 2009. *The Castle of Lamia*, Ministry of Culture and Sports, Athens
- Papakonstantinou, M.F. & D. Sakkas. 2010. "Middle Helladic Pottery from Amouri in the Spercheios Valley." In: *MESOHELLADIKA. The Greek Mainland in the Middle Bronze Age. Proceedings of the International Conference, Athens 8-12 March 2006*, BCH Suppl. 52: 583-90, edited by A. Philippa-Touchais, G. Touchais, S. Voutsaki & J. Wright, Athens: French School at Athens.
- Schramm R., Use of X-ray Fluorescence Analysis for the Determination of Rare Earth Elements, *Physical Sciences Reviews*, (2016) 20160061
- Selvaraj Th., Gallelo G., Mehra A., Rungta K., Jaganathan B., Ramacciotti M., Pastor A., Raneri S. (2024). Rare earth elements sediment analysis tracing anthropogenic activities in the stratigraphic sequence of Alagankulam (India). *Heliyon*. 10. e29767. [10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29767](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29767)
- Vranova V, Marfo Th. D and Rejsek Kl, 2015, *Soil Scientific Research Methods Used in Archaeology - Promising Soil Biochemistry: A Mini Review*, *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, <https://doi.org/10.11118/actaun201563041417>

APPENDIX

Table 1. Average concentration of major elements of the samples, estimated by p-XRF (oxides in wt% normalized to 100%)

	CONCENTRATION (wt%)					
	SiO ₂	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	MnO	Fe ₂ O ₃
L1/1	32.2	1.7	25.0	0.34	0.12	3.6
L1/2	13.4	1.5	21.9	0.33	0.09	3.5
L1/3	28.7	1.6	24.7	0.32	0.10	3.3
L1/4	31.0	1.6	25.0	0.36	0.11	3.7
L1/5	31.4	1.8	23.8	0.34	0.10	3.6
L4/1	27.2	1.6	17.4	0.33	0.10	3.4
L4/2	38.6	1.8	19.0	0.38	0.11	4.2
L4/3	14.4	1.3	18.5	0.33	0.10	3.5
L4/4	28.7	2.0	21.7	0.35	0.10	3.8
L4/5	32.0	1.7	21.7	0.34	0.10	3.8
L5/1	25.2	1.7	21.1	0.36	0.10	4.0
L5/2	26.3	1.6	21.6	0.34	0.09	3.7
L5/3	17.4	1.6	18.1	0.37	0.10	3.9
L5/4	24.4	2.0	20.2	0.36	0.09	3.8
L5/5	19.9	1.6	20.8	0.31	0.09	3.6
L5/6	31.3	1.8	20.6	0.33	0.10	4.0
L6/1	30.8	2.1	18.3	0.37	0.10	3.8
L7/1	21.1	2.1	13.7	0.46	0.10	4.5
L7/2	30.8	2.2	20.6	0.36	0.08	3.4
L7/3	32.5	2.2	24.2	0.33	0.09	3.4
L8/U1/1	21.7	2.3	27.4	0.30	0.06	2.7
L8/U1/2	25.9	2.5	27.0	0.32	0.06	2.8
L8/U1/3	20.0	2.4	27.1	0.30	0.06	2.7
L8/U1/4	25.6	2.4	28.6	0.30	0.07	2.6
L8/U1/5	28.0	2.6	30.5	0.31	0.06	2.7
L8/U1/6	18.0	2.4	29.2	0.30	0.06	2.6
L8/U2/1	24.5	2.5	27.1	0.32	0.07	2.8
L8/U2/2	21.8	2.3	26.9	0.31	0.07	2.8
L8/U2/3	24.9	2.4	27.3	0.32	0.07	2.9
L8/U3/1A	20.7	2.0	23.2	0.30	0.08	3.2
L8/U3/1B	26.0	2.2	23.9	0.32	0.08	3.4
L9/U1/1	35.9	2.2	17.5	0.39	0.09	3.8
L9/U1/2	26.6	2.4	21.3	0.37	0.08	3.4
L9/U1/3	26.3	2.6	20.6	0.37	0.09	3.5
L9/U2/1	25.2	2.4	23.0	0.34	0.08	3.3
L9/U2/2	25.1	2.4	27.7	0.31	0.07	2.8
L9/U2/3	27.7	2.4	29.9	0.30	0.07	2.8
L9/U2/4	32.6	2.5	27.1	0.33	0.07	3.0
L9/U3/1	32.7	2.3	25.5	0.34	0.08	3.3

L9/U3/2	32.0	2.6	26.4	0.34	0.07	3.1
L9/U3/3	28.2	2.4	25.1	0.35	0.08	3.4
L9/U3/4	21.6	2.4	34.6	0.27	0.05	2.5
L9/U3/5	34.6	2.5	24.0	0.34	0.07	3.2
L9/U3/6	27.2	2.3	27.5	0.31	0.07	3.0

Table 2. Average concentration of minor and trace elements of the samples, estimated by p-XRF (element form in ppm)

	CONCENTRATION (ppm)																	
	V	Cr	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Se	Br	Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Ba	La	Ce	Nd	Pb	Th
L1/1	59	220	301	94	148	11	-	12	55	214	16	120	231	13	45	15	61	4.9
L1/2	45	213	292	73	126	11	1.8	10	53	181	17	131	183	12	44	13	59	5.4
L1/3	50	203	288	88	138	12	1.8	12	53	204	17	121	217	13	46	15	54	5.0
L1/4	61	277	279	86	146	12	1.9	11	53	209	17	127	204	13	46	15	57	5.5
L1/5	65	312	327	88	142	13	1.2	12	54	203	17	123	197	13	44	15	48	5.8
L4/1	49	276	306	80	135	16	1.4	11	58	177	18	133	187	13	48	16	84	4.6
L4/2	56	326	397	81	137	13	1.5	10	53	168	18	138	159	12	43	15	54	5.0
L4/3	51	213	299	73	126	12	1.7	11	56	182	17	129	185	12	42	12	56	5.4
L4/4	50	234	356	81	123	12	1.6	9	55	189	17	121	182	13	46	18	38	6.3
L4/5	59	300	367	75	123	12	1.4	10	56	187	17	129	190	13	45	14	39	5.9
L5/1	60	293	345	84	129	13	1.4	11	53	193	18	128	159	12	43	15	40	5.5
L5/2	54	253	318	77	127	13	1.7	12	53	192	17	122	170	12	44	15	57	5.5
L5/3	62	327	335	84	140	15	1.6	15	60	180	18	133	232	15	49	18	46	6.0
L5/4	62	293	366	90	137	15	1.5	14	62	199	17	128	231	15	48	16	50	6.2
L5/5	59	526	409	97	156	17	1.7	13	59	198	17	127	206	15	47	15	36	5.7
L5/6	58	286	379	102	136	16	1.6	27	58	193	18	131	239	15	46	15	52	5.8
L6/1	61	243	318	88	145	16	1.6	15	54	189	18	138	245	16	48	15	48	5.8
L7/1	89	161	192	189	104	15	-	9	85	157	21	154	260	18	55	19	41	8.9
L7/2	64	237	229	61	114	13	1.5	7	72	212	19	135	235	16	51	18	33	7.9
L7/3	66	206	262	67	118	15	1.7	8	68	227	18	133	225	15	50	15	32	6.9
L8/U1/1	48	131	161	40	92	15	1.5	5	56	281	20	128	225	18	56	14	46	6.1
L8/U1/2	46	232	179	43	92	14	1.6	4	75	292	21	131	207	16	53	18	26	7.0
L8/U1/3	46	114	170	38	89	14	1.8	4	77	299	21	127	232	19	56	20	26	6.8
L8/U1/4	50	122	152	37	88	14	1.9	5	77	292	21	129	245	20	57	19	27	7.1
L8/U1/5	46	124	153	37	87	15	1.6	3	76	311	21	128	240	18	54	19	25	7.8
L8/U1/6	53	197	166	36	84	14	2.0	4	56	312	20	126	271	19	56	12	56	5.4
L8/U2/1	49	132	177	43	94	14	2.2	4	76	293	22	132	209	18	53	20	26	7.2
L8/U2/2	49	131	185	45	98	14	2.0	5	75	288	21	128	258	18	56	20	27	7.3
L8/U2/3	58	131	185	44	98	14	1.6	4	78	287	21	129	223	17	54	19	26	6.8
L8/U3/1A	55	347	355	58	132	16	1.6	9	66	221	19	130	218	14	50	18	33	7.0
L8/U3/1B	58	235	392	66	146	14	1.6	10	55	232	18	127	215	15	47	18	38	6.3
L9/U1/1	75	232	226	71	130	18	1.4	17	73	181	19	138	228	17	53	18	30	7.0
L9/U1/2	73	204	196	67	121	15	1.6	11	74	218	19	133	229	16	50	18	34	7.9
L9/U1/3	63	174	213	65	127	14	1.6	11	74	210	20	144	254	16	51	18	35	7.2
L9/U2/1	67	164	215	66	111	18	1.9	8	77	215	19	137	263	17	53	18	29	7.5
L9/U2/2	56	115	172	44	93	13	2.0	5	81	281	21	132	245	19	56	20	26	6.9

L9/U2/3	49	118	200	43	91	13	1.9	5	76	294	20	123	224	18	52	18	28	6.2
L9/U2/4	59	130	180	57	104	14	2.4	6	79	258	20	132	277	17	54	20	29	7.2
L9/U3/1	62	135	204	60	105	18	2.2	8	56	208	20	128	284	17	55	14	39	5.9
L9/U3/2	60	127	191	57	102	17	1.8	8	75	224	19	127	288	17	55	19	25	7.5
L9/U3/3	66	201	217	65	111	18	1.2	7	76	217	20	136	424	18	56	21	28	8.4
L9/U3/4	48	100	148	56	86	27	1.9	10	65	224	19	124	231	16	52	17	22	7.3
L9/U3/5	51	142	203	55	105	16	2.1	8	77	226	20	134	255	18	54	18	28	7.8
L9/U3/6	57	118	192	62	101	23	1.3	9	53	215	20	126	278	18	56	15	40	5.5

Table 3. Average concentration of major elements of representative samples from each layer, estimated by SEM/EDS (oxide form in wt%, normalized to 100%; "nd": not detected)

Samples	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	FeO
L1	0.99	4.18	12.78	43.86	2.91	nd	3.05	27.52	nd	6.01
L4	0.61	4.56	10.77	47.29	3.15	nd	2.46	23.46	0.81	6.88
L5	1.19	4.68	10.06	45.45	3.78	6.54	2.99	22.49	nd	6.89
L6	2.02	4.43	12.82	49.53	5.52	3.69	3.76	21.22	nd	7.01
L7	0.81	4.01	10.69	43.73	1.96	5.22	3.24	24.47	nd	5.86
L8	0.71	4.31	11.03	42.52	1.92	nd	3.49	28.86	0.93	7.70
L9	0.84	3.41	12.24	43.51	1.75	6.60	3.33	24.35	0.59	5.99